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ABSTRACTS

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Aptamer tethered hetero-polymer conjugated mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNPs) mediated delivery of dual siRNA to induce apoptosis in breast cancer cells

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Abstract:The study aimed to explore the gene silencing potential of multifunctional aptamer-tethered hetero-polymer conjugated mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNPs) loaded with dual small interfering RNAs (siRNAs) in MCF-7 breast cancer cells. Objectives included synthesizing and characterizing hetero-polymer conjugated MSNPs, attaching polyethylene glycol (PEG) and MUC-1 aptamer onto the Nano carriers, and evaluating gene silencing efficacy. MSNPs were synthesized via sol-gel technique, conjugated with hetero-polymer molecules, and subsequently modified with PEG and MUC-1 aptamer. Characterization involved dynamic light scattering (DLS), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR). Quantitative real-time PCR assessed the gene silencing efficacy of dual siRNAs (MCL-1 and Survivin) loaded onto the aptamer-modified MSNPs in MCF-7 cells, complemented by a cell death assay. FTIR and zeta potential measurements confirmed successful hetero-polymer conjugation onto MSNPs. Targeted Nano carriers significantly suppressed the target genes compared to non-targeted ones and lipofectamine 2000. Cell death assays verified apoptosis induction through Caspase assays. In conclusion, aptamer-modified hetero-polymer conjugated MSNPs hold promise for delivering therapeutic agents in MCF-7 cells. Dual targeting of anti-apoptotic genes exhibited enhanced efficacy in inhibiting cancer growth compared to single-gene targeting, suggesting potential avenues for future targeted breast cancer therapies.

Keywords: Gene silencing, Aptamer, siRNA, Mesoporous silica nanoparticles, Targeted therapy, Dual siRNA, Breast cancer, MUC-1 aptamer.

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